

Simple Synthesis of 1,4-Dioxa-2,3-dioxocyclopentadec-6-ene from Aleuritic Acid

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Synthesis of 1,4-dioxa-2,3-dioxocyclopentadec-6-ene has been achieved from *threo*-aleuritic acid (9,10,16-trihydroxyhexadecanoic acid).

Literature reports the synthesis of cyclic dilactone, 4-methyl-2,6-dioxa-1,7-dioxoheptadecane, a perfumery compound used in food industry as aroma/flavour, from dodecanedioic acid and 2-methyl-1,3-propanediol¹. Macrocyclic diesters like 1,4-dioxa-2,3-dioxocyclohexadecane having musk-like odour are also used in food and perfumery industries², synthesized from the respective diols and diacids. This prompted us to synthesize hitherto unknown 1,4-dioxa-2,3-dioxocyclopentadec-6-ene (**6**), an analog having musk-like odour from *threo*-aleuritic acid (**1**) which can easily be obtained by alkaline hydrolysis of shellac and subsequent isolation³. Compound **1** on periodate oxidation⁴ afforded 9-oxononanoic acid (**2**) as one of the intermediate products, which was treated with malonic acid in the presence of pyridine to yield the unsaturated dioic acid (**3**). Its dimethyl ester (**4**) on reduction with LAH/THF yielded (*E*)-2-undecene-1,11-diol (**5**) which on reflux with diethyl oxalate in toluene containing catalytic amount of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid gave a polymer. It was depolymerized under reduced pressure in the presence of MgCl₂·6H₂O to yield the title compound **6**.

Experimental

B.ps. and m.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrometer, nmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 instrument using TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on a JMS-D 300 spectrometer. The compounds were routinely checked for their purity by tlc.

9-Oxononanoic acid (2) : *threo*-Aleuritic acid (32 g, 0.105 mol) was treated with NaOH solution (4.2 g, 0.105 mol) in water (126 ml). Chloroform (126 ml) was then added followed by NaIO₄ (26.9 g, 0.125 mol) in lot for 15 min. The solution was shaken at 40° for another 15 min and processed following the reported procedure⁴ to yield **2** as a liquid (16.7 g); ν_{\max} (neat) 1725, 1700 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃)

1.11–1.81 (10H, m (CH₂)₅CH₂COOH), 2.3 (4H, t, *J* 6 Hz, CH₂CHO), 9.54 (1H t, *J* 2 Hz, CHO), 9.87 (1H, b s, COOH).

(E)-2-Undecene-1,11-dioic acid (3) : The above acid aldehyde (**2**, 3.5 g) was heated on a steam-bath with malonic acid (3.5 g) in the presence of dry pyridine (16 ml) till CO₂ evolution ceased. On usual work up with ether, a solid was obtained, which on crystallisation from ethyl acetate gave white needles of the title acid (2.7 g), m.p. 95–97° (lit.⁵ 95–97°) (Found : C, 61.62; H, 8.40. C₁₁H₁₈O₄ calcd. for : C, 61.67; H, 8.41%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1700, 970 cm⁻¹ (–HC=CH).

Dimethyl-(E)-2-undecene-1,11-dioate (4) : **3** (3 g) dissolved in dry methanol (30 ml) containing catalytic amount of conc. H₂SO₄ was refluxed on a steam-bath for 6 h. On usual work-up with ether **4** was obtained as a liquid (yield 90%), which was purified by column chromatography; ν_{\max} (neat) 1730, 968 (CH^ECH) cm⁻¹ (Found : C, 60.41; H, 9.08. C₁₃H₂₂O₄ requires C, 60.44; H, 9.09%).

(E)-2-Undecene-1,11-diol (5) : **4** (2.0 g) was reduced by LAH (0.2 g) in dry THF (20 ml) on a steam-bath for 8 h and worked up to obtain **5** as a liquid (1.5 g) which was then purified by column chromatography (Found : C, 70.90; H, 11.81. C₁₁H₂₂O₂ requires : C, 70.96; H, 11.82%); ν_{\max} (neat) 3450 (OH), 970 (CH^ECH) cm⁻¹.

1,4-Dioxa-2,3-dioxocyclopentadec-6-ene (6) : Refluxing a mixture of **5** (6.7 g), diethyl oxalate (7.31 g) and PTSA (0.05 g) in toluene (100 ml) for 10 h and on usual work-up a polymer (11.5 g) was obtained as liquid, which was depolymerised under reduced pressure (75 mm) with MgCl₂·6H₂O (0.2 g) at 210–20° (bath temp.) to give **6** as a liquid (68%) : ν_{\max} (neat) 2870, 2840 (C–H), 1680 (C=O), 1640 (C–C), (CH^ECH) 965 cm⁻¹ (CH bend); δ (CDCl₃) 5.47, 5.65 (2H, m, (CH^ECH)), 3.73 (2H, t *J* 7 Hz, CH₂CH₂–O–CO), 2.2 (2H, q, *J* 7 Hz, CH₂–CH=CHCH₂O), 1.63 (2H, m, CH₂CH₂OCO), 1.33 (10H, br s, (CH₂)_n); *m/z* 240 (M⁺), 192 (M–CO₂), 144 (M–2CO₂) 98 ((CH₂)₇), 54 (CH₂=CHC⁺HCH₂).

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NOTE

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